

Exploring the Mechanical and Toxicological Properties of Concrete by Partially Replacing Fine Aggregates with Periwinkle shells Particulates

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Abstract

This study aimed to examine the impact of periwinkle shell particles (PSP) on the concrete compressive strength, and to assess the environmental risks associated with its leachates. In this study, different concrete samples were produced by partially replacing fine aggregates with varying proportions of PSP at levels of 0%, 5%, 10%, 15%, and 20%. The concrete specimens were cured using total immersion, and both their compressive strength and the physiochemical properties of the curing water were assessed on the 28th day. The concrete compressive strength results indicated an uneven decline from 26.3 to 13.17 MPa as the PSP volume integrated into the concrete inclined from 0 to 20%. Similarly, It was observed that as the quantity of periwinkle shell particles (PSP) increased from 0% to 20%, the pH values rose from 9.21 to 11.60, dissolved oxygen levels decreased from 7.70 to 3.63 mg/L, biochemical oxygen demand values increased from 2.12 to 9.30 mg/L, the total dissolved solids (TDS) levels rose from 69.00 to 85.85 mg/L, and the nitrate concentrations increased from 0.63 to 1.90 mg/L. Remarkably, the research findings revealed that incorporating a small amount of PSP (approximately 10%), as a partial replacement for sand during concrete production, can produce concrete with a reasonable compressive strength (greater than 17 MPa) and environmentally friendly leachates. This approach helps combat the negative effects of climate change by minimizing the depletion of natural sand and reducing the carbon footprint associated with conventional building materials.

Keywords: Climate change, eco-toxicity, marine sand, public health, sustainable materials.

Introduction

Concrete is a fundamental construction material typically made by mixing cement, water, sand, and gravel at a right proportion. The cement acts as the binding material for the aggregates (sand and gravel) while water helps to hydrate the cement and helps to create a workable composite. Concrete has become a trusted construction material due to its durability, high compressive strength, and resistance to heat and fire (Omar Tanash *et al.*, 2023). When properly maintained, concretes are durable, withstanding harsh environmental conditions, including anthropogenic activities. High quality concrete can be produced from sustainable materials and recycled aggregates, therefore reducing carbon footprint and mitigating climate change effects (Owamah *et al.*, 2024).

Recently, numerous scientific studies have focused on incorporating organic sustainable materials in the fabrication of concrete and sandcrete blocks. This shift is driven by the need to mitigate the environmental hazards posed by the use of inorganic building materials, such as increased greenhouse gas emissions and resource depletion (Akpokodje *et al.*, 2021; Chamasemani *et al.*, 2023; Fasasi, 2024). The production of many inorganic materials used for building construction releases emissions that increase the amount of greenhouse gases (GHGs) in the atmospheric air component (Eřtoková *et al.*, 2022). These GHGs includes carbon oxides, methane, and nitrous oxides, which can accumulate in the atmosphere leading to the reduction of the thickness of the ozone stratum, and exacerbating the menace associated with climate change, such as global warming and other extreme weather actions (de_Richter *et al.*, 2017; Mehra *et al.*, 2021).

Many construction materials, particularly concrete, are significant contributors to environmental pollution, as they can release substantial amounts of pollutants into the environment (Mohamad *et al.*, 2022; Nilimaa, 2023). When concrete and sandcrete blocks degrade, they can release particulate matter and chemicals into the ecosystems leading to broader environmental concerns (Alaa and Muthusamy, 2022). Effluents discharged from both organic and inorganic building materials can have significant impacts on ecosystems. These discharges often contain chemicals, pollutants, and waste products that can degrade soil and water quality, harm aquatic life, and disrupt natural habitats. Organic materials tend to reduce the DO, increase the BOD and nitrate content of water bodies. Owamah *et al.* (2024) stated that leachate from organic-based sustainable materials used for concrete production, can increase the Biological Oxygen Demand (BOD) of curing water, leading to changes in the water's physicochemical properties and potentially elevating toxic metal concentrations. This disruption can upset the natural balance of ecosystems, as it affects oxygen levels in water bodies, leading to conditions that may harm aquatic life and reduce biodiversity (Rodrigues *et al.*, 2022).

Although several studies have explored the environmental impact of leachates from bio-concretes, a review of related literature reveals a gap in information regarding the effects of effluents from concrete produced using sawdust on the environment. Therefore, this investigation is aimed to investigate the impact of leachate from sawdust concrete on environmental quality, focusing on how it alters water chemistry, soil properties, and potential ecological risks associated with its use.

Materials and methods

Materials

Fine aggregates

Marine sand (sharp sand) was used as the fine aggregates (sand) in the course of the concrete production. The sand used in this study was air-dried to reduce its moisture content to 20% of its natural moisture level. This was necessary because high moisture levels in the sand can reduce the compressive strength of the resulting concrete. Excess water interferes with the hydration process of cement, weakening the chemical bonds that form during the curing process (Eboibi *et al.*, 2022).

Periwinkle shells particles

The periwinkle shells were crushed and sifted with a 2.25 mm sieved size to obtain the fine periwinkle shells particulates (PSP), later used as partial replacement for the sand.

Coarse aggregates

Granite of the size 19 mm was the coarse aggregates employed for the concrete production.

Cement and Water

Limestone Portland cement (grade 42.5) was the binder used to produce the concrete blocks. The water used in the experiment was clear and free from visible foreign materials, with a pH value of 7.4.

Methods

Sieve analysis

The sand sieve analysis (particle size grading) was conducted in compliance with the standard methods outlined in ASTM C136 (2006), ensuring accurate particle size grading for concrete production.

Concrete mix design

For this research, the sand was partly substituted with 0, 5, 10, 15 and 20% of periwinkle shell particles (PSP).

Concrete production

The concrete mix ratio used in this research was 1:2:4, which indicates one part cement, two parts fine aggregates (sand), and four parts of coarse aggregate (gravel). A water-to-cement ratio (w/c) of 0.5 was employed to ensure adequate workability and strength development. The concrete cubes were cast in standard moulds with dimensions of 0.15 m by 0.15 m by 0.15 m.

Concrete curing

The cast concrete cubes were detached from their respective moulds after 24 hours, and subsequently cured using the total immersion technique.

Concrete compressive strength determination

The compressive strength was measured following the ASTM C109 / C109M (2020) standard guidelines by using the concrete Compression Testing Machine (Model: STYE 2000, produced in China), to ensure accurate and consistent compressive strength results. The concrete's compressive strength was computed employing the expression in Equation 1.

$$\text{Compressive Strength} = \frac{\text{Failure Load}}{\text{Cross-sectional Area}}$$

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Physiochemical chemical properties of the concrete leachate determination

The pH, biological oxygen demand (BOD), dissolved oxygen (DO), total dissolved solids (TDS), and nitrate content of the leachates were analyzed following ASTM International-approved guidelines. These parameters are critical for evaluating the environmental impact of leachates, as they affect water quality and can have ecological and health implications.

Statistical analysis

The data collected in this study were analyzed statistically using Microsoft Excel 2010 software. For each particular test, it was carried out in triplicate and the average documented.

Results and Discussion

Particle size grading (PSD)

The data from the sharp sand PSD analysis are presented in Figure 1, providing a graphical representation of the results. The soil exhibited a fines content of 3.0% and a uniformity coefficient (C_u) value of 7.7, classifying it as well-graded according to the Unified Soil Classification System (USCS) soil classification system (ASTM D2487, 2017). Soils with a well-graded particle distribution are often associated with the production of high-strength and long-lasting concrete, making them a preferred choice for concrete manufacturing applications (Oyelami *et al.*, 2016; Ogunbayo *et al.*, 2021).

Figure 1: The PSD plot

Compressive strength

The results of the concrete compressive strength are illustrated in Figure 2, where it was noted that the concrete strength decreased irregularly from 26.3 to 13.17 MPa as the volume

of periwinkle shell particles (PSP) raise from 0 to 20%. The rapid deterioration in the concrete mechanical strength as the PSP increases could be linked to poor bonding efficiency between the organic particles and the cement matrix, which disrupt the setting and strength development of the composite structure (Ghazanlou *et al.*, 2021; Obukoeroro and Uguru, 2021). Interestingly, despite the overall decline in concrete compressive strength with increasing PSP volume, it was observed that using a smaller proportion (around 10%) of periwinkle shell particles (PSP) as a partial replacement for sand can still yield concrete with appreciable strength (17 MPa) suitable for residential buildings. This affirms Olofinnade *et al.* (2023) report which stated that at moderate levels, periwinkle shells waste can be incorporated into cement composite without significantly compromising the structural integrity of the product formed. This study reveals that using sustainable alternative materials, such as periwinkle shells, can significantly decrease the reliance on natural sand in construction projects, ultimately contributing to environmental preservation and mitigating the negative impacts of climate change.

Figure 2: The concrete samples compressive strength at 28th curing day (MPa)

Physicochemical properties of the curing water

The physicochemical properties of concrete leachates are summarized in Table 1, highlighting the key findings and characteristics of the leachates. The pH values of leachate water increases as the periwinkle shells fillers volume incorporated into the concrete specimens increased. It was noted that the pH values of the concrete produced with 0, 5, 10, 15 and 20% PSP where 9.21, 10.50, 10.89, 11.17 and 11.60, respectively; while the DO values were 7.70, 6.23, 4.73, 4.10 and 3.63 mg/L respectively. Likewise, the discharge from the concrete made with 0, 5, 10, 15 and 20% PSP had BOD values of 2.12, 3.75, 5.58, 6.76 and 9.30 mg/L, respectively; while the TDS values were 69.00, 73.02, 76.89, 79.88 and 85.85 mg/L, respectively. Additionally, it was noted that the curing water recovered from the 0, 5, 10, 15 and 20% PSP integrated concrete, had nitrate values of 0.63, 0.98, 1.25, 1.45 and 1.90 mg/L, respectively. The results are comparable to those previously observed for other concrete composite samples made from green materials by Mocová *et al.* (2019). According

to Nurul *et al.* (2019), the inclusion of organic materials in cement matrix composites can lead to an increase in the BOD and chemical oxygen demand (COD) of the leachates produced by the composite. Elevated BOD and COD values indicate higher levels of organic and chemical pollutants, which can have significant hazards on the ecosystems, affecting water quality and ecosystem balance (Owamah *et al.*, 2024).

Table 1: The curing water physicochemical properties

Sample (%PSP)	pH	DO (mg/L)	BOD (mg/L)	TDS (mg/L)	Nitrate (mg/L)
Control (0%)	9.21±0.18	7.70±0.17	2.12±0.04	69.00±3.78	0.63±0.02
5%	10.50±0.15	6.23±0.08	3.75±0.06	73.02±1.99	0.98±0.05
10%	10.89±0.09	4.73±0.08	5.58±0.34	76.89±1.19	1.25±0.07
15%	11.17±0.14	4.10±0.12	6.76±0.24	79.88±1.43	1.45±0.05
20%	11.60±0.14	3.63±0.32	9.30±0.11	85.85±1.91	1.90±0.07

Conclusion

This research was conducted to appraise the impact of periwinkle shell particles (PSP) on the concrete compressive strength, and the environmental hazards associated its leachates. In this study, different concrete samples were produced through partially replacement of fine aggregates with 0, 5, 10, 15 and 20% of PSP. The results depicted that the inclusion of PSP had a distinguished impact on both the concrete compressive strength, and the physiochemical properties of the leachates produced from the concrete. The presence of the PSP in the concrete mixture significantly impacted the water's chemical properties, causing a decrease in dissolved oxygen levels (DO) and an increase in pH, biological oxygen demand (BOD), total dissolved solids (TDS), and nitrate levels. This research outcome reveals that incorporating PSP into concrete leads to a decrease in compressive strength, but surprisingly, a small amount of PSP (approximately 10%) can be utilized to manufacture concrete with acceptable compressive strength for residential building construction. This research revealed that the utilization of sustainable alternative materials, such as periwinkle shells, can make a substantial impact on reducing the demand for natural sand in construction projects. By incorporating these materials, not only are natural resources preserved, but also environmental conservation efforts are furthered.

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